

INFLUENCE OF NANOPARTICLES ON METAL ION CATALYZED OXIDATION OF MODEL SUBSTRATES BY METHYLENE BLUE IN ACIDIC MEDIUM**Ranu Chaturvedi**Department of P.G. studies and research in Chemistry and Pharmacy,
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Abstract: - The catalytic activity of metal ions is attributed to the formation and participation of metal nanoparticles in homogeneous - heterogeneous domain. Studies indicates a change in morphology of metal ion-substrate nanoparticles from nanorods to nanogranules on adding another metal ion to the reaction system. Metal ions have unique properties including redox/electron transfer and diverse oxidation states and coordination number due to which metal and metal compounds have tremendous potential and wide applications in various fields. The present paper highlights the interaction of bioactive sulfhydryl substrates, glutathione, cysteine hydrochloride and 2- mercaptoethylamine hydrochloride with methylene blue in acidic medium in a mole ratio of 2:1 forming the corresponding disulfide and dihydromethylene blue (leucobase) in acidic medium. In the present system the catalytic property of metal ions is due to the formation of nanoparticles & their multifacet involvement in metabolic pathways have attracted considerable attention. Thus, these studies, on metal nanoparticle , catalysed oxidation of model substrates paves the way to understand the complex chemistry of such systems.

Keywords: metal ion catalysis, nanoparticles, model substrates.

INTRODUCTION

The concept of metal ion catalysis is not new but its immense application in various fields especially in metal-thiolate ligation has attracted a considerable attention mainly due to the multifacet involvement of these systems in metabolic pathways [1-7]. It has been realized that certain enzymes contain thiolate bridged assemblies of the general formula $Fe_4S_4(X)M$ in which Fe_4S_4 cubane is covalently linked to another metal ion by thiolate(s) or sulphides [8]. Recently, the use of nitrosyl radicals alone or in combination with transition metals as catalysts in oxidation processes has been exploited for synthetic as well as mechanistic view point [9]. It is also realized that the catalytic activity of metal ions in some cases is attributed to the formation and participation of metal nanoparticles in homogeneous - heterogeneous domain [10, 11]. It has been reported that addition of cesium (I) and rhenium (VII) ions remarkably increase the catalytic activity of homogeneous poly (acrylic acid)-stabilized silver (PAA-Ag) nanoclusters. Heterogeneous

palladium nanoclusters, acting as a catalyst, were immobilized on chelate resin-metal ion complexes, and were prepared by reduction of palladium (II) ions supported on resin complexes [12]. The catalytic activity of nanoparticles is attributed to the existence of enormous number of active sites available to the reactants and the efficiency of nanoparticle catalyst is known to depend on various factors such as porosity, morphology , size ,phase composition, solvent etc.[13]. Metal ion catalysis involving participation of nanoparticles and sulfur chemistry have attracted considerable attention mainly due to the multifacet involvement of these systems in metabolic pathways. In the light of this, comparative metal ion catalyzed oxidation of bioactive sulfhydryl substrates by a model electron receptor methylene blue (MB) have been studied in acidic medium.

EXPERIMENTAL AND RESULTS

The solutions of the substrates ,oxidant - methylene blue (MB) and metal ions were prepared by dissolving an exactly weighed

a slope of 0.96 . The rate of reaction is not influenced by the time of equilibration of the catalyst with other ingredients of the reaction system excluding MB which is in contrast with the observations made for Ru(III) catalyzed oxidation of cysteine with this oxidant [15]. The addition of the corresponding disulfides did not produce a change in the rate. The rate of reaction again remains unaffected on adding dihydromethylene blue to the system in the oxidation of cysteine whereas in the oxidation of 2-ME, the rate of reaction slightly decreases with increasing the concentration of leuco base. The time of equilibration of the metal ion with other ingredients of the reaction system did not affect the rate in 2-ME.

The activation parameters of the reactions were evaluated by making the runs at different temperatures ranging between 25 and 45°C. ΔH^* , ΔS^* and ΔG^* for the oxidation of cysteine, 2-ME and glutathione were calculated by the use of Eyring equation, van't Hoff isochore equation and by using Arrhenius plots. These were compared and it was found that all these oxidation reactions are accompanied by the negative entropy of activation.

$$-\frac{d[MB]}{dt} = k_1[RSH][Cu(II)] \left\{ \frac{k_{-1}[H^+](k_3 K [MB] [H^+] + k_{-2}) + k_2 k_3 K [Zn(II)] [MB]}{k_{-1} k_3 K [MB] [H^+] + k_{-1} k_{-2} [H^+] + k_2 k_3 K [Zn(II)] [MB]} \right\} \quad (14)$$

and for Ru(III) catalysed oxidation of glutathione ,the rate is given by [14]

$$-\frac{d[MB]}{dt} = \frac{3k_1 K_1^{2/3} K_2 [Ru(III)] [RSH]}{[H^+]} \quad (21)$$

These rate equations explain almost all the characteristic feature of the reaction system. Formation of nanoparticles within the reaction system plays a very important role in metal ion catalysed redox systems. Among various metal particles copper nanoparticles are attracting a greater attention because of their optical , catalytic and electrical conducting properties at a significantly lower cost than gold and silver. Copper nanoparticles being cheaper , require mild conditions for high yield of products in a

DISCUSSION

Rate equation has been formulated for all these systems by considering the protonation of MB to MBH⁺ and the coordination of substrate with a metal ion to form an unstable complex formed in situ. It seems that this complex C₁ perhaps facilitates an intramolecular rearrangement in the substrate molecules as a consequence of the participation of nanoparticles. Complex C₁ may interact with protonated methylene blue molecule (MBH⁺) to produce a transient species C* while Cu(II) , hydrogen ion and (Zn (II) are liberated. The transient species C* may subsequently dissociate to give radicals RS[•] and HM[•] (half reduced methylene blue radical) which in turn, may interact with the substrate molecule to give the end products. Incidentally, the participation of radicals such as RS[•] and HM[•] in these reaction systems has been frequently reported in the literature [19,20]. By considering the formation of C* as a rate determining step and applying the steady state treatment for the transient species the rate of reaction is given by [18]

short time as compared to a traditional catalyst and can be exploited in many industrially important reactions such as Biginelli reaction, in the reduction of aromatic nitro compounds to aromatic amino compounds in the presence of tetra hydro furanes THF/H₂O and sodium borohydride in the synthesis of 2- arylbenzoxazoles by the coupling of aromatic or heteroaromatic aldehydes with 2- aminophenol through the oxidative cyclization of the Schiff's base using Cu nanoparticles in the presence of

K_2CO_3 in methanol etc. so Cu will gain increasing importance as it is expected to be an essential component in the future nano devices due to its excellent conductivity as well as good biocompatibility and its surface enhanced Raman scattering activity [21]. In the present case, the catalytic activity of Cu(II) is due to the formation of Cu-cysteine nanorods as revealed by transmission electron microscopy. Zn-cysteine interaction also gives indications of the formation of nanoparticles but they are low-melting and thus, could not be characterized. It has already been recorded that the morphology of the nanoparticles changes in presence of Zn (II) and nanogranules are obtained. Glutathione (γ -glutamylcysteinylglycine) which is an important bioactive sulphhydryl compound protects the -SH group of different proteins and enzymes from oxidation, deactivation and radiation injury besides being a model system for the binding of metal ions especially those involved in the toxicology. Recently glutathione (GSH) - decorated magnetic nanoparticles for binding glutathione-s-transferase (GST) fusion protein and manipulating live cells have been prepared [22]. Studies on cosensitization properties of GSH- protected Au_{25} cluster on ruthenium dye -sensitized TiO_2 photoelectrode suggests that GSH- protected Au_{25} clusters should behave as both a coadsorbent to increase active sensitizer, which opens new methodologies for the design of coadsorbents with sensitization properties [23]. In addition to this nanoparticle based delivery and release system using GSH as the releasing agent can be further utilized to realize delivery of proteins and enhance transfection of genetic materials [24]. These studies with different view point clearly highlights the importance of metal ion catalysed oxidation of model substrates which is basically due to the formation and participation of nanoparticles & this paves way for further studies in the future.

CONCLUSIONS:

The reaction between substrates cysteine hydrochloride , 2- mercaptoethylamine

hydrochloride and glutathione by methylene blue catalyzed by metal ions in acidic medium shows the formation and participation of nanoparticles. Studies indicates a change in morphology of metal ion-substrate nanoparticles from nanorods to nanogranules on adding another metal ion to the reaction system. It has already been mentioned by Komalam and coworkers that these metal nanoparticles helps the electron relay from the donor to the acceptor. The particles possess large surface area which acts as the substrate for the electron transfer reaction. Just before the electron transfer reaction both of the reactants are adsorbed on the metal particle . Subsequently the reactant gains an electron and is reduced . Thus, the metal particles act as an efficient catalyst in the electron transfer process. Such studies on metal nanoparticle catalysed oxidation of model substrates paves the way to understand the complex chemistry of such systems.

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